

A CROSS SECTIONAL ANALYSIS OF ATTITUDE TOWARDS TRANSGENDER

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Abstract

Transgender community face extreme exclusion in our society due to various misconceptions and reasons. The aim of the study was to explain attitudes of sample based on educational qualifications and the cisgender. Descriptive survey method was adopted to study the attitude of 540 respondents from various educational background. The t test results indicated that there is no significant difference between attitudes of cisgender towards transgender. Further, ANOVA indicated that there is no significant difference in the attitude towards transgender based on educational qualification except between groups of respondents with SSC and others (below SSC). The results to a great extent indicates that education plays an important role in broadening horizons and accepting individuals as they are without any judgement.

Key Words: *Transgender, Attitude, Hijra*

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Introduction

Transgender people face extreme exclusion in the society. This exclusion is due to the strong societal endorsement of binary notions of gender. Hence, the society stigmatizes via the internalization of negative attitude towards them. A person's slight deviation from the normative beliefs results them to be labelled as transgender, one who is non-conforming to the common belief and attitude in the binary scale. In the Indian context they are labelled as hijras, although different labels are given in different cultures and context. Hijra is an umbrella term used for those men who are transgender, eunuch, transvestites, and hermaphrodites or intersexed, bisexuals or homosexuals (Nanda, as cited in Brettell & Sargent, 1997; Sharma, 2000).

Need

Hijra is considered physically and psychologically ambivalent and because of ambivalence people consider them freaks (hiding their sexual identity). Therefore, they are a marginalized/ stigmatized community. Article 19 of the Constitution of India declares nondiscriminatory practices on the basis of religion, race and gender yet; several instances of stigma and discrimination prevail among the sexual minorities in India including the hijras.

The Indian society at large have sanctioned and given a place to hijras (especially during weddings, births, festivals) but at the same time they lack a respectable place in the society. Due to non-conformity in binary notion, the transgender are denied gender recognition certificate, sexual expression, employment, decent housing, subsidized health care services. They face violence especially when they choose to take up sex work. Transgender are not given their space and freedom. They are constrained to conform to the dichotomy of gender.

Review

Regression analysis of an internet-based survey, by Elischberger, H.B., Glazier, J.J., Hill, E.D. et al. examined attitudes toward transgender youth in the United States and India. The findings revealed positive attitudes toward transgender youth of U.S. (n = 218), but moderately negative ones in Indian (n = 217), sample. It accounted for considerably more of the variability in U.S. than in Indian participants. Contrasting attitude and beliefs emerged between U.S. and Indian participants.

A study conducted in Tamil Nadu on the discrimination faced by hijras in sex work, in the Indian health-care system highlighted that the health care professionals do not know anything about them and do not treat them like other patients. They are often addressed in a disrespectful manner and the staff frequently uses male pronouns which they find very offensive.

Norton, A.T., Herek, G.M. study showed attitudes toward transgender people were more negative among heterosexual men than women. sexual prejudice accounted for much of the variance in transgender attitudes, but respondent gender, educational level, authoritarianism, anti-egalitarianism, and (for women) religiosity remained significant predictors with sexual prejudice statistically controlled.

Aim: To study the attitude of cross section people of the society towards transgender.

Objective:

1. To study attitude of people towards transgender based on educational qualifications:
 - a. under graduates
 - b. graduates
 - c. postgraduates
 - d. professionals
2. To study the attitude of cisgender towards transgender.

Hypothesis:

1. There is no cisgender significant difference in the attitude towards transgender.
2. There is not significant difference in the attitude towards transgender based on educational qualification:
 - a. SSC,HSC and others
 - b. graduates
 - c. postgraduates

Methodology Descriptive comparative method was adopted for this study. The researcher wanted to know if there is any difference in the attitude of the sample towards transgender on the basis of gender (binary classification) and the educational qualification.

The **sample** size for the study was 540. Following table shows the nature and composition of the sample:

Table 1: Nature and composition of the sample

Variable	Number	Variable	Number	Variable	Number	Variable	Number	Variable	Number
Male	287	SSC	14	B.A	29	M.COM	35	Medical	13
Female	253	HSC	36	B.COM	124	M.SC	24	Education	32
		Others (less than SSC)	52	B.SC	34	M.A.	13	C.A	16
				Commerce Specialisation	39			Engineer	35
								Law	14
								MBA	30
Total	540	Total	102	Total Graduates	226	Total Post Graduates	72	Total Professionals	140

Table 2 Relevant Statistics for 't' test for cisgender comparison of attitude towards transgender

	<i>Female</i>	<i>Male</i>
Mean	217.0348	219.6364
Variance	449.9219	590.8434
Observations	287	253
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	504	
t Stat	-1.31682	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.094249	
t Critical one-tail		1.647883
P(T<=t) two-tail		0.188497
t Critical two-tail		1.964682

The 't' value of 1.31 is less than the t Critical value of 1.96. Thus, we accept the null hypothesis.

There is no cisgender significant difference in the attitude towards transgender.

Probably the reasons may be that in contemporary times, with education people's attitude towards transgender has seen change with society opening up to accept them and include them in mainstream.

Table 3 Relevant Statistics for ‘f’ test for comparison of attitude of SSC, HSC and others towards transgender

Result Details					Pairwise Comparisons		
Source	SS	df	MS		HSD _{.05} = 14.9781	HSD _{.01} = 18.7708	Q _{.05} = 3.3651 Q _{.01} = 4.2172
Between-treatments	3380.0775	2	1695.0387	F = 3.37778	T ₁ :T ₂	M ₁ = 231.57 M ₂ = 219.08	12.49 Q = 2.81 (p = .12152)
Within-treatments	49680.2363	99	501.8206		T ₁ :T ₃	M ₁ = 231.57 M ₃ = 214.13	17.44 Q = 3.92 (p = .01821)
Total	53070.3137	101			T ₂ :T ₃	M ₂ = 219.08 M ₃ = 214.13	4.95 Q = 1.11 (p = .71238)

The F-ratio value is 3.37778. The p-value is .038101. The result is significant at $p < .05$.

The f ratio value of 3.38 indicates that there is a significant difference in the attitude towards transgender based on educational qualifications where groups were SSC, HSC and others (less than SSC qualification) were compared. Tukey HSD indicated a significant difference in the mean scores of group 1 and group 3 i.e. SSC and others (less than SSC). Probable reason is that education does broaden the horizon of thinking. Education helps to accept individuals as they are.

Table 4 Relevant Statistics for ‘f’ test for comparison of attitude of graduates from Arts, Commerce, Science and respondents with Specialization in commerce towards transgender

Result Details				
Source	SS	df	MS	
Between-treatments	1537.4724	3	512.4908	F = 0.9346
Within-treatments	121733.948	222	548.3511	
Total	123271.4204	225		

The F-ratio value is 0.9346. The p-value is .424735. The result is not significant at $p < .05$.

The f test result of 0.93 indicated that there is no significant difference of graduates (B.A, B.Com, B.Sc and Graduates in Commerce Specialization) attitude towards transgender

Table 5 Relevant Statistics for ‘f’ test for comparison of attitude of post-graduates from Commerce, Science and Arts towards transgender

Result Details				
Source	SS	df	MS	
Between-treatments	1454.0534	2	727.0267	F = 2.37587
Within-treatments	21114.266	69	306.0039	
Total	22568.3194	71		

The F-ratio value is 2.37587. The p-value is .100496. The result is not significant at $p < .05$.

The f test result of 2.38 indicated that there is no significant difference in the post-graduates (M.Com, M.Sc, M.A) attitude towards transgender

Conclusions

A relook at the provisions for the transgender needs attention. The results indicated that education has an important role to play to bring about the change in the attitude of individuals towards transgender. They are now denied the various rights that a citizen enjoys such as right to get a passport, ration card, voters identity card, pan card and various other rights. They do not have access to education, marriage, earning livelihood etc.

The status of transgender changed when they were given recognition by Supreme Court of India which recognized them as the **third gender** affirming that the fundamental rights granted by the Constitution of India to the citizens will be equally applicable to them also. Public awareness programmes will play a pivotal role in tackling the stigma attached to the transgender community. Legal recognition should be granted to bring them in the societal mainstream. Constitutional and legal provisions should be equally accessible to the transgender community. They should be accepted as individuals without stigmatizing them. The transgender community should have what they are rightfully given constitutionally and legally.

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